

A Research Opportunity ... Evidence of Ritual Burial Customs on a Nephrite Gui with Cover. Possibly from Liangzhu to late Shang Dynasty.

Width (handle to handle ... 23.5cm
Rim diameter ... 14cm
Base diameter ... 17.5cm
Height ... 10cm.
Thickness approx. 0.7cm
Weight 2.0 Kg

Abstract

A lidded nephrite gui probably from the Liangzhu through to late Shang Dynasty. This exceptional vessel forms a triumvirate with the only two other recorded lidded jade guis found up to the end of the Shang Dynasty. One is from the Liangzhu Dynasty the other from the Liao Dynasty. Both are probably located in Chinese museums or collections. (Locations unknown.) Robert Bradlow (Sotheby's/Christies) has confirmed this gui is 'of age'.

This gui shares characteristics found on early nephrite examples: There is plain evidence that it has been subject to extensive wear and handling. Also the demanding procedure of hollowing out, reveals the incredibly fine and closely spaced parallel tooling grooves, also found on vessels from the suggested periods. Other tool marks also comply.

The attention to detail, design and craftsmanship of this gui are of the highest order. It is unfinished. It would have been a hugely ambitious project. The design feature of the parallel grooves show the symmetry and precision associated with the Liangzhu Dynasty. Of course these parallel grooves are also a recognised feature of the Shang Dynasty.

Perhaps unique, is the evidence of both ritual damage and remnants of red ochre/hematite pigment on this gui. There is clear evidence of deliberate repetitive scoring, chisel and gouge marks. These can be identified from what appears to be thousands of minor scratches and surface abrasions caused by wear and handling. Of interest is the ability to see exactly those scratches and score marks inflicted pre burial ... and post burial. There are red ochre pigment remnants on the surface of the scratch/score marks inflicted before burial. A useful indicator of the timeline.

When we observe these ritually inflicted score marks, either in parallel pairs or even as a serried row of scored 'X' marks, it is an action we can readily associate with. It stirs an emotional ancestral bond to form a tangible connection with that person from our distant past.

The red ochre pigment indicates an elite or royal burial. The gui has a two character inscription. The evidence indicates the gui was in use for a considerably period of time before consigning to the grave. Perhaps the inscription was added then?

This image shows some of the deliberate diagonal ritual scoring marks. The precision of the tooled parallel grooves is apparent. Regular horizontal parallel tooling marks can be seen on the vessels surface.

The lower part of the perfectly tooled parallel grooves show these regular 'V' tool marks. Indicative of a chisel/burin type tool.

XRF Spectrum

The analysis shows an Fe/Mg ratio of 0.5—0.7. This shows us the nephrite is high in actinolite (with the high fe reading) which often results in the dark olive green colour. The main vessel, lid and handles all have a similar elemental signature. There are some black hematite inclusions. Different sample points provide readings which do vary showing the nephrite is not homogenous. .

The orange line is a nephrite pebble for comparison. The blue line is the gui spectrum.

Weathered Appearance.

The elemental composition of this nephrite gui indicates ferro actinolite. It can be seen that the XRF spectrum closely resembles the nephrite pebble ... which is translucent. However this gui is opaque (Reflectance spectroscopy spectrum is near identical to green earth), perhaps originally so, or an effect of burial?

For comparison purposes of weathered surfaces. On the left the disc is late Neolithic.

Weathering/alteration of the guis surface.

At some stage this vessel has been cleaned ('opening the window') However, the removal of surface accreditations still leaves traces visible to microscopic examination.

There is much evidence of re-crystallisation on the vessel's surface. Hair, acicular and plate crystals. It can be seen from the image that the plate crystals are shiny and reflective. In the image of the hair crystal it can be seen that it is bridging a tooled groove which has remnants of red ochre. It is of note that these delicate hair crystals have only survived, where there is significant remaining red pigment,

There are numerous areas of lustrous shiny white crystalline outcrops as seen in this micrograph.

Twin acicular crystals have formed over heavy red ochre remnants. Damp conditions as found in burials are necessary for these crystals to develop.

Diverse weathering effects.

Red Ochre

It is well documented that vermilion or red ochre/hematite pigment was liberally applied to elite burial goods. Red Ochre is indicative of earlier burials. (Fuhao's tomb is an example.) The Han Dynasty saw the prevalence of vermilion used in elite burials. The red staining on this gui tests for red ochre. Varying in intensity, presumably because of the cleaning regime. While some red/brown marks may be the result of the high fe content the morphology is different from that evidenced on this gui. It seems that the whole vessel, inside and out was liberally coated with this pigment.

Whilst it is recorded that jade items were often found damaged at burial sites the use of either red ochre or vermilion to cover the grave goods was less common. It is highly likely that such a rare and ritualistically important vessel, such as this, would be only associated with a royal burial.

The above image is of a 3000 year old burial item with identified red ochre staining. It can be seen that the morphology of the pigment is similar. The left hand image also shows more lustrous plate crystallisation and twin acicula crystals.

The red ochre pigment remnants are visible to the naked eye in some parts of the tooled grooves. It is apparent that it is more visible in those areas which have proved to be harder to clean. Close to the handles is a good example.

Ritual Damage

Repetitive diagonal scores on this gui indicate deliberate attempts to damage it. This is, perhaps, a unique surviving example of the process of ritual damage, to a vessel before burial? Additionally the more vulnerable edges of the rim, cover and a protruding handle have been broken. There are seven repairs. There is a narrow crack. Fortunately, presumably because of the felt nature of nephrite, it is not continuous.

Repetitive diagonal scoring and gouging.

“Jade burial items from the Shang Dynasty have been found intentionally chiselled before burial, reflecting the belief that damaging the objects would release the spiritual energy. Also this will make them more potent for their intended use in the afterlife.”

Here there are a line of repetitively scored 'X' marks on the vessels lid.

There are also more heavily scored repetitive marks. Presumably inflicted with a larger chisel. Gouge marks are also evidenced.

However there are numerous abrasions, and chips as seen here on the topside of the cover seemingly caused by usage. Many minor scratches are also visible.

Damage ... cont.

Whilst score marks in the centre section of the base look repetitive, and therefore deliberate, the general condition around the circumference looks more to be the result of general usage.

It has been recorded that an item may have been used by multiple generations before being consigned to a burial.

This is a micrograph of the inflicted score marks. It can be seen that the red ochre staining is significantly lighter in intensity above the re-crystallisation..

This is to be expected where the crystallisation has 'pushed through' a surface layer of pigment, and therefore dissipating it.

If the red ochre had been applied after re-crystallisation it would have a similar intensity as that on the rest of the vessel.

The vast majority of scratches have red ochre remnants indicating the vessel was in use for a considerable time before burial.

Tool marks.

There is a central hole in the vessels lid. Characteristic, fine concentric circular abrasions, are similar to marks left by hollow, probably bamboo or bone, drill and an abrasive. The principal entry hole is cone shaped. The underside has a lip... indicating the hole has been 'knocked through'. There appears to be a step ... or ledge halfway through the hole. Perhaps indicating the use of a substitute 'drill'?

*Top of lid showing irregular cone shape entry.
There is a lip that partly overhangs.*

The exit hole has been knocked through. Evidenced by the lip. The irregular striations are visible ... with some smooth areas. It can be seen that there is a small step or ledge halfway through the hole. Perhaps a change of the drilling feature?

The hole shows evidence of re-crystallisation.

Micrograph showing striations.

Tool marks.

A view of the interior of the Gui. To the naked eye the tooled finishing grooves look reasonably parallel ... and extremely closely spaced.

The deeper scores are presumably the result of a coarser grain of abrasive.

It is recorded how difficult the hollowing out process of a bowl was. Unlike a cong which could be drilled right through. The proposed method used was to drill with a slightly tapering cone shape, (wood or metal sheet fabricated) using abrasives and slurry. Then great skill was needed to strike the central portion to remove. Possibly with the help of more drilled small diagonal diameter holes. The remaining irregular mass then had to be removed.

Whilst it appears the outer one third circumference was finally cut with string to remove the waste, the central portion is uneven indicating an ad hoc approach was used with the tools which were available.

The inside walls of the gui show the characteristic fine closely spaced parallel grooves. The grooves are 0.125mm wide and are spaced 0.125mm apart. So there are four grooves occupying 1mm. This surely confirms the use of fine grain abrasives? Roger Keverne has commented on these 'impossibly spaced' fine grooves which appear from the Liangzhu Culture. Apparently there appears to be no reference to these exact tool marks on items tooled after the Shang Dynasty.

“Minutely separated parallel ridges or striations, in some instances four or five parallel lines can be found in a band no more than 1mm wide.” Roger Keverne

It has been suggested that an extremely fine pointed rotary lathe type tool may have been used. Whilst not discounting these theories; it seems suggestive that these tool marks may be also produced by drilling. Simply because these grooves are extremely similar to those produced by tool marks on cong and gui of the suggested period(s). Indicative of this type of drilling is that the concentric lines are not always regular. Some diverge and some are disrupted. (A modern diamond drill produces perfect parallel grooves.) The spacing between the grooves is dictated by the abrasive used. Carborundum being the finest. The occasional coarser grain will produce a more deeply scored groove.

Perhaps it is suffice to say that the tool marks shown comply with those found on attributed artefacts.

Tool Marks cont.

1mm

A micrograph shows that some of the (interior) tooled grooves diverge. Others are disrupted. Research has indicated that the only way these tool marks can be produced is using a hand drilling (slow) technique and slurry. (with abrasive.)

This is the interior of the vessel showing the base. It can be seen that the craftsman somehow removed the outer one third of the circumference by string cutting. The shallow undulating irregular wave pattern has been identified as only originating from string cutting.

The central portion is uneven ... suggesting it was 'hacked' out, with perhaps, a chisel.

Design

A distinctive stylistic feature of Liangzhu and Shang Dynasty jades are the closely spaced parallel grooves. Perfectly tooled. The convex effect achieved through these incised grooves was a deliberate artistic choice. As seen below the grooves vary in width. This characteristic has been observed on other Shang Dynasty items. Employed for artistic effect.

The design, attention to detail and quality of craftsmanship of this gui are exceptional. The closely spaced parallel tooled grooves and consequential symmetry of this gui perhaps indicate mid to late Shang Dynasty from a stylistic angle?

The artist has tooled these grooves with exceptional accuracy. But he has also deliberately tooled different widths for overall effect. The handles are just roughly tooled and therefore unfinished.

There is a narrow groove of 0.3mm on the top rim.

Mirroring the lowest pair of grooves ... the top groove is 0.3mm wide. The one below is 0.6mm wide.

This pair of tooled grooves are of identical width ... 0.8mm

The higher groove is 0.6mm wide.

The lowest groove is just 1mm from the base. This groove is 0.3mm wide.

The profile of the 'V' cut grooves. It can be seen the right hand (wider) groove is cut at an oblique angle. It has been observed that craftsman often used this approach with a sharp pointed burin. Has the craftsman deliberately used two different techniques to achieve these different groove widths?

Design cont.

Considerably artistry and craftsmanship has been employed with the cover.

The wide central band slightly inclines to the centre. The handle is deeply undercut. With a recessed area to accommodate fingers when lifting off. The central hole may be to vent steam or for the ritualistic positioning of vertical chopsticks as an offering to the dead. There can be little doubt that this cover is designed and tooled by an exceptional craftsman. Was the undertaking of a jade gui and cover simply too difficult and time consuming? Is that why we know of only two other extant examples? Or was it because bronze examples could be cast relatively quickly?

It can be seen from the right hand image that the artist has continued the theme of the pairs of parallel lines in the recess for the handle.

The lower image shows the coarse finishing grooves of the underside of the cover. Perhaps left deliberately? There are some indications that this gui is unfinished. The handles bear rough chiselling marks and are clearly unfinished.

The drilled hole in the centre of the underside of the cover. The interesting question is:

- Was this a vent hole for steam?
- Was this hole drilled, to enable the ritual of placing vertical chopsticks, in offerings to the dead?

The base is the only section which does not bear tool marks. Presumably this is because it has been ground away to a deep saucer shape. Thus reducing the contact surface area as normally found with guis. (To reduce heat loss.)

Inscription

There is what appears to be a two character inscription close to one of the handles. It is recorded that very short, often single or two character inscriptions, were prevalent in the Shang Dynasty. Often denoting the clan name. Subsequently, inscriptions were longer.

The evidence of the somewhat fainter red ochre staining on top of the re-crystallisation shows the inscription was pre burial

The two character inscription.

The image on the top left shows a late Shang Dynasty inscription. It can be seen that the arrowed character (and adjacent) bears a similarity to the lower character on the gui.

Speculation

It is recorded that it was not uncommon for jade items to be inscribed at a later date than when they were made. Often the inscription would be carved before the item was consigned to a burial.

It can be seen that, the red circled character on the left hand image, bears quite a close similarity with that on this gui. The stone tablet with the inscription was unearthed from a high rank tomb from Cao-Wei period in Xizhucun cemetery, Henan.

Whilst it would be hugely speculative to link the two, the timing would account for the amount of wear and tear seemingly caused by usage on the gui. More realistically perhaps this comparison will assist in the identification of the inscription?

Overview

It is undeniable that a craftsman at the top of his craft undertook this hugely ambitious project. Why was it not finished?

Ill health or death perhaps? Death of a ruler? Apart from, the inflicted deliberate damage, there are a huge number of minor scratches and pits. It is possible that this gui was used for many generations before burial. It may have been unearthed and used again. Consequently it would have gone through cleaning regimes. Ferro Actinolite only has a hardness of 5-6 on the Mohs hardness scale. So quite susceptible to scratching. It was traditional to scrub away the calcification ('opening the window'). It may have also been cleaned in more recent times. However, any cleaning process can only be superficial, as revealed by the micrographs.

The examination of the surface showing the repetitive inflicted scoring, combined with the red ochre staining, gives us evidence of the ritual burial customs. Surely a person of high rank? Additionally the huge number of minor scratches indicate that this gui has been in use for many generations?

Consequently this gui appears to be an important, and perhaps unique, addition to our knowledge and the historical record?

This Gui has been confirmed to be 'of age' by a Christies expert. My field, as such, is fine art. Consequently there may well be inaccuracies in this research; most likely in the conclusions drawn. I invite researchers, museums or perhaps a university, to take the opportunity for a professional investigation and analysis of this fascinating piece of history. Please contact me at aspong1@gmail.com